

Medicinal plants used in the treatment of Alzheimer's Disease: A Review

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Abstract- 1906, a general physician, Dr Alois Alzheimer, reported the presence of pathological deformity in the necropsied brain of a woman affected by Alzheimer's Disease (AD). The disease is associated with behavioral issues, difficulties in daily activities, and a diversity of neuropsychiatric symptoms. Diagnosis of the disease in the early stage is essential. At an early stage, it is difficult to differentiate between normal ageing and disease symptoms. Psychological and neurological characteristics like apathy, aggression, depression, and psychosis are considered core features of Alzheimer's disease. The major pathological hallmark of the disease includes neurofibrillary tangles and senile plaques. Conventional practices of medicine, using different parts of numerous plants in their various forms to treat several neurodegenerative disorders, including cognitive disorders such as Alzheimer's disease. This traditional approach, when combined with modern technology, helps identify new leads for potential drugs. This article aims to identify key aspects related to AD.

Keywords - Neurotransmitter, Alzheimer's disease, ethnopharmacological, cognitive, plaque.

I. INTRODUCTION

AD (Alzheimer's disease) is a neurodegenerative disease that develops over a period of time and damages mental ability and disturbs cognitive functions[1]. The term neurodegenerative disease applies to a variety of mental conditions that develop due to the deterioration of the neurons of the central nervous system[2]. AD is the prime cause of dementia, which mostly occurs in people above the age of 60. Nearly 50-75 % of dementia is due to Alzheimer's disease[3-11]. Worldwide statistical data reveal females are more susceptible to Alzheimer's disease relative to males, and the risk rises more with age[12]. People with diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease are also at elevated risk of having Alzheimer's disease. Autopsy reports of AD patients in the early 1970s disclosed that acetylcholine release and choline uptake are lessened in the brains of AD patients. This observation led to the introduction of the cholinergic hypothesis[13].

There is no permanent remedy for AD so far; medication available only can reduce its progression. It is declared as a "Global public health priority" by the World Health Organization[14]. AD has a progressive nature and eventually leads to a severe cognitive decline. It mainly affects elderly people older than 65 years, called Late Onset of AD (LOAD). The other type is familial Alzheimer's disease or EOAD (Early Onset of Alzheimer's Disease), i.e., three persons in a family have AD initiated at an early stage of life[15]. Nearly 25% of AD is familial, and 75% is the non-familial type, i.e., an individual with AD but no family history of AD observed [16].

1.1 EOAD (Early Onset of Alzheimer's Disease)-

Early onset of AD is a dementing neurodegenerative disorder that is relatively rare (<1% of all Alzheimer's cases). In early onset cases, symptoms unfold before the age of 60. This type is rarer than late-onset Alzheimer's disease. However, it tends to worsen rapidly; early onset of disease can occur in more than one member of a family, with a mean starting age of before 60 years. The characteristics of the early onset type are similar to those of the late onset type of AD[17-18]. Various studies revealed genetic mutations of the presenilin1, presenilin2, and APP (amyloid precursor protein) gene. Mutations of Presenilin1 and Presenilin2 alter the γ -secretase enzyme that cleaves APP and produces a relatively increased amount of amyloidogenic A β 42 [19].

1.2 LOAD (Late Onset of Alzheimer's Disease) -

Most of the cases of Alzheimer's disease are of the late-onset type. It typically appears in elderly people above the age of 60. The role of the gene in the development of its symptoms is less clear[20].

1.3 Four different phases of AD, based on cognitive decline and histopathological alterations from clinical points, are: the preclinical stage, the Mild stage, the Moderate stage, and the Late-Stage AD [21].

1.3.1 Preclinical stage-

At this stage, no severe symptoms are present; only minor impairment in cognition is observed. The earliest pathological changes begin and initially affect the frontal cortex, followed by the hippocampus.

1.3.2 Mild Stage -

This stage starts with the manifestation of cognitive symptoms. The pathological changes, accompanied by memory loss, affect the cerebral cortex, resulting in difficulty remembering and learning new information, forgetting appointments and other important details, deterioration in judgment, impaired task performance, and reduced ability to perform administrative work. Additionally, the patient exhibits mood swings, a loss of spontaneity, and personality changes. Further, disorientation and confusion are very common at this stage.

1.3.3 Moderate stage -

At this stage, the severity of the disease symptoms increases as the pathological damage spreads to areas responsible for reasoning, language, and processing, i.e., the cerebral cortex. Also, behavior issues and social alienation tendencies become visible, followed by damage to visual-spatial skills and speech problems.

1.3.4 Severe Alzheimer's Disease-

At this stage, patients are unable to perform their routine work and are completely dependent on others for daily activities. The pathological damage covers almost the entire cortex area. From a symptomological point of view, a patient's cognitive ability was almost lost at this stage. Moreover, systematic symptoms begin to appear, including olfactory dysfunction, difficulty in carrying out learned motor tasks (dyspraxia), sleep disturbances, and extrapyramidal motor signs such as akinesia, dystonia, and Parkinsonian symptoms [22-30].

The brains of AD patients exhibit several changes, including the selective depletion of neurotransmitter systems, such as acetylcholine (ACh) in the cerebral cortex and hippocampus, as well as the loss of neurons, synapses, and atrophy [31-33].

1.4. Acetylcholine –

Acetylcholine is a neurotransmitter liberated at the nerve ending. It is an organic molecule produced by the enzyme choline acetyltransferase, which utilizes choline and acetyl-Coenzyme A in specific cells known as cholinergic neurons [34-39]. Insufficient neurotransmitters and disturbances in cholinergic functions are identified as common pathological features in central nervous system disorders. A loss of ACh is considered to play a crucial role in the memory deterioration and learning process in AD patients. Caring for patients with this disease requires considerable emotional, financial, and social support. Researchers have found that environmental factors, as well as genetic factors, are also responsible for the initiation of AD [40]. Genetic factors consider heredity, family history, and age, while environmental factors include long-term exposure to metal dust particles or silicon, chronic exposure to free radical damage, other toxins, and brain injury due to trauma [41].

Currently, symptomatically, in the treatment of AD, include agents like –

- Galantamine, rivastigmine, Donepezil, etc. – AChEIs (acetylcholinesterase inhibitors) and
- Memantine - NMDA (N-methyl D-aspartate) [42-43].

II. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

A German physician, Dr Alois Alzheimer, in 1906, collected the brain cells of a woman named Auguste D. and specifically identified abnormalities in it. Her family brought her to Dr Alzheimer in 1901. Later, he described Auguste as having an aggressive form of dementia and died after years of experiencing difficulty in understanding questions, confusion and memory problems [44]. He performed an autopsy on the dead brain cell. He found nerve cells bearing dense deposits around and outside of them. He further noticed twisted bands of fibres inside the nerve cells. After all his findings, this degenerative brain disorder bears his name and is called Alzheimer's disease [45].

III. EPIDEMIOLOGY

Alzheimer's is one of the most common brain disorders found in elderly people, which raises alarm to the general public's mental health, leading to enormous personal and economic costs worldwide. The occurrence of disease is more common (1.5 times) than epilepsy or stroke. While primarily affecting the elderly, it is rare among younger individuals. In the United States, it is estimated that around 4 million people are living with Alzheimer's, while globally the number reaches nearly 15 million. As the population continues to age, the number of individuals with Alzheimer's is rising rapidly. The disease affects 10 % of people over the age of 65 years and about 50% people over the age of 85 years [46-47].

According to a Canadian study of health and ageing, approximately 1 in 20 Canadians over the age of is affected by Alzheimer's Disease. In 2001, an estimated 238,000 Canadians were living with the condition, with about 60,000 new cases projected each year. These trends indicate AD will potentially be the most overwhelming public health problem in this country [48].

IV.MECHANISM OF TRANSMISSION OF ACETYL-CHOLINE IN CHOLINERGIC NEURONS

According to various studies, the acetylcholine released in the central nervous system is found to be involved in regulating mood, learning, and memory. Acetylcholine, a chemical substance, is synthesized in the presynaptic terminal from acetylcholine and CoA by the action of the enzyme choline acetyltransferase (ChAT). It is stored at the presynaptic terminal in the form of a synaptic vesicle. Synaptic transmission begins at the presynaptic terminal with depolarisation of the neuronal cell membrane [49]. Depolarisation of the membrane opens Ca^{+2} channels present in the presynaptic membrane. Ca^{+2} then admit into the terminals. The Ca^{+2} promotes the fusion of the synaptic vesicle to the presynaptic membrane. The synaptic vesicles become confluent with the open terminal membrane and release their content into the synaptic cleft [50]. Once released, the transmitter diffuses quickly across the synaptic cleft and binds to specific receptor proteins on the postsynaptic membrane. A large no of proteins, such as vampsyntaxin, synap, and synaptotagmin, have been implicated in the binding of the synaptic vesicle to the presynaptic membrane [51]. These proteins form complexes between the synaptic vesicle and the presynaptic terminals, enabling the vesicle to dock to the membrane.

4.1 Cholinergic receptors –

Two cholinergic receptors are named nicotinic receptors and muscarinic receptors. Upon activation, nicotinic receptors directly result in the depolarisation of neurons. They are located at synapses between two neurons and skeletal muscle cells, while muscarinic receptors trigger a chain of chemical events referred to as signal transduction. It is located at the synapses of nerves with smooth or cardiac muscles [52].

When Ach binds to the receptor in the post-synaptic terminal, a conformational change occurs in the protein, allowing the $Na^{+}-K^{+}$ channel in the receptor to open and permeate Na^{+} ions into the post-synaptic vesicles. This builds up a positive charge inside the membrane, known as an EPSP (excitatory postsynaptic potential). When the EPSP reaches the threshold, an action potential is generated in the neuron and information is released. After releasing the information, the Ach in the post-synaptic receptor is hydrolysed by the enzyme AchE to acetate and choline and thus, terminating the synaptic activity [53]. Choline is actively transported back into the presynaptic neurons and combines with acetyl-CoA to form ACh in the presence of the enzyme ChAT. Finally, synaptic vesicles are formed by the folding of the terminal membrane (away from active zones) and the separation of that membrane to form a vesicle. The Ach is then restored in the synaptic vesicles for subsequent chemical transmission, and the transmission is complete [54-55].

V.PATHOGENESIS

The key features of AD's pathogenesis are the gradual deposition of the beta-amyloid protein fragments outside of neurons and twisted tangle fibres of tau protein inside neurons in the brain.

Beta-amyloid plaques prevent neuron-to-neuron communication at synapses and function as a neurotoxin, while the tau tangle protein causes axonal transport dysfunction and neuronal loss by preventing the passage of essential molecules and nutrients inside neurons [56-58]. Apart from these two causes, memory impairment is also associated with cholinergic dysfunction, which involves receptors, their neurons and neurotransmitters.

Dysfunction of the cholinergic system occurs due to the degeneration of the cholinergic neurons in the basal forebrain and hippocampus, leading to the decline in cognitive abilities [59-60]. In contrast, in healthy individuals, stimulation of the central cholinergic system promotes hippocampal neurogenesis through the cAMP response element-binding protein/brain-derived neurotrophic factor (CREB/BDNF) signaling pathway [61].

5.1 Pathological Manifestations -

Multiple pathogenic mechanisms are found to be involved in the onset and progression of the disease, including plaque formation, inflammation activation, oxidative stress, and cholinergic dysfunction.

5.2 Amyloid Plaque -

Neurotic plaques are spherical microscopic lesions composed of a core and the extracellular amyloid β ($A\beta$) peptide, surrounded by abnormal axonal endings. These $A\beta$ particles are derived from a larger protein known as the Amyloid precursor protein (APP). APP can be cleaved by three enzymes, including α -, β -, and γ -secretase. Under normal conditions, APP is first cut by α -secretase, followed by γ -secretase, a process that prevents the generation of $A\beta$ peptides. However, when the β -secretase enzyme cleaves the APP molecule, it releases soluble amyloid precursor protein β (sAPP β) from the cell. Subsequent cleavage by γ -secretase produces $A\beta_{40}$, $A\beta_{42}$, and C99 fragments of amino acids. Elevated levels of $A\beta_{42}$ promote the formation of oligomers, which possess neurotoxic effects. In Alzheimer's disease, these toxic oligomers accumulate around cerebral and meningeal vessels, as well as in the grey matter [62].

5.3 Neurofibrillary Tangles -

Neurofibrillary tangles are fibrillar, intracytoplasmic structures found within neurons, primarily composed of the protein called tau. Under normal conditions, tau plays an essential role in stabilising axonal microtubules. In

Alzheimer's Disease (AD), however, tau becomes abnormally hyperphosphorylated, leading to its aggregation inside neurons. Over time, this disrupts neuronal function, impairs communications between cells and ultimately causes cell death. Because of this abnormal tau accumulation, AD is classified as a tauopathy. In affected neurons, chemically altered tau loses its ability to maintain microtubule integrity. Hyperphosphorylation, often mediated by protein kinases, causes the cytoskeleton to disintegrate, leading to the breakdown of the intracellular transport system between nerve cells and ultimately resulting in neuronal degeneration [63].

5.4 Oxidative Stress -

Recent research suggests that oxidative stress and the generation of free radicals are key contributing factors in the development of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Free radicals promote the formation of advanced glycation end products, nitration, lipid peroxidation adducts, carbonyl-modified neurofilament proteins and free carbonyls; ultimately contributing to neuronal damage and eventual cell death. Furthermore, oxidative stress can enhance amyloidogenic processing of β -amyloid precursor protein (β -APP), leading to the accumulation of neurotoxic $A\beta$ species. Evidence also indicates that β -amyloid toxicity increases the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and lipid peroxidation in neuronal cultures. Elevated oxidative stress is strongly associated with synaptic dysfunction and memory impairment in AD [64].

5.5 Dendritic Hypothesis -

Dendritic abnormalities are evident in the early stages of Alzheimer's disease (AD), with features such as dystrophic neuritis, reduced dendritic complexity, and loss of dendritic spines being well-documented. Evidence suggests that soluble $A\beta$ oligomers are the primary neurotoxic agent responsible for dendritic pathology [65].

5.6 Cholinergic Imbalance -

One of the earliest pathological events in Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is believed to be the dysfunction and loss of basal forebrain cholinergic neurons along with their cortical projections. Within the neuronal system, two primary types of cholinesterase (ChE) are present: acetylcholinesterase (AChE), predominantly associated with cholinergic neurons, and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE), also called pseudocholinesterase or nonspecific ChEs, which is a serine hydrolase linked to glial cells and specific cholinergic pathways. These enzymes are highly efficient with the ability to hydrolyse more than 10,000 molecules of acetylcholine (ACh) per molecule of ChE. Normally, acetylcholine (ACh) is synthesised in cholinergic neurons by choline acetyltransferase, stored in synaptic vesicles, and released from presynaptic terminals following depolarisation. Under pathological conditions, excessive ChE activity reduces acetyl choline availability, ultimately impairing neurotransmission. Moreover, AChE facilitates $A\beta$ aggregation, while elevated cortical levels of BuChE have been strongly associated with neurotoxic plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, which are major pathological features of AD. Consequently, inhibitors of AChE and BuChE are currently major therapeutic targets in AD treatment strategies.

Another characteristic feature of AD is granulovacuolar degeneration within hippocampal pyramidal neurons. This degeneration is thought to contribute to cognitive impairment, as an alteration in cognitive processes correlates with a reduction in presynaptic bouton density in pyramidal neurons of Laminae III and IV [66].

5.7 Genetics -

Alzheimer's disease shows a strong genetic link to three specific genes: the amyloid precursor protein (APP) gene and the genes encoding the Presenilin 1 (PSEN1) and Presenilin 2 (PSEN2). Mutations in any of these genes are closely associated with the development of amyloid plaques. Research indicates that individuals carrying mutations in the APP or PSEN1 genes will inevitably develop AD, whereas those with mutations in the PSEN2 gene have a 95% likelihood of experiencing the condition. When AD arises due to alterations in these three genes, it is classified as autosomal dominant familial AD. Beyond these three causative genes, only one other gene has been strongly linked to the AD risk: the apolipoprotein E (APOE) gene, which encodes for the apolipoprotein E protein and plays a critical role in binding lipids and sterols and transporting them through the circulatory and lymphatic systems. In the brain, its primary function is to regulate cholesterol transport [67].

5.8 Role of Metal Ions -

Beyond genetic and other contributing factors, metal ions play a significant role in $A\beta$ -mediated toxicity in the brain of individuals with Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Research has shown that elevated levels of Al, Zn, Cu and Fe in the brain can trigger free radical generation, promote protein and DNA oxidation and increase lipid peroxidation in AD. Additionally, the aggregation and structural conformation of the $A\beta$ peptide are strongly influenced by both the peptide concentration and the levels of three specific metal ions — Cu, Zn, and Fe. Studies further suggested that Cu(II), Zn(II), and Fe(III) bind to $A\beta$ with high affinity. These ions are found in particularly high concentrations in the neocortex, the brain region where amyloid plaques are most prevalent [68].

5.9 Protein Glycation and Alzheimer's Disease -

Glycation phenomena have been implicated in the etiology of many age-related pathologies. Glycation of protein starts as a non-enzymatic process with the spontaneous condensation of an aldehyde or ketone group of a sugar with a free amino acid to form a labile Schiff base consistent with the classical reaction first described by Millard in 1912. This initial reaction triggers a cascade of chemical transformations, ultimately leading to the production of advanced glycation end products (AGEs). AGEs are irreversible, cross-linked, and heterogeneous protein aggregates that can contribute to cellular damage and disease progression [69].

VI. AD AS A METABOLIC DISORDER

Clinical evidence suggests that diabetes is a significant risk factor contributing to the development of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Studies have demonstrated a strong association between insulin-deficient diabetes and cerebral amyloidosis. Both conditions appear to involve impairments in insulin signaling within the central nervous system and periphery. Peripheral and central insulin signaling impairment is likely present in both diseases. As a result, the type 3 diabetes hypothesis of AD was developed. The insulin hormone is at the center of this hypothesis [70].

6.1 Mitochondrial Anomalies and Alzheimer's Disease -

Defects in the mitochondrial electron transport chain are a major factor contributing to the overproduction of free radicals. Numerous studies have reported reduced oxidative phosphorylation in AD, a deficit that manifests both as diminished energy production and the accumulation of potentially toxic free radicals. The electron transport chain, responsible for generating ATP through the reduction of oxygen to water, is a complex enzymatic system composed of five sequential components: Complex I (NADH dehydrogenase), Complex II (succinate dehydrogenase), Complex III (Ubiquinol cytochrome-c reductase), Complex IV (cytochrome-c Oxidase) and Complex V (ATP synthase). Alterations in mitochondrial function have been observed during aging and in various neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and Huntington's disease. In AD, especially, the most notable impairment occurs in complex IV, where cytochrome c oxidase activity is reduced by approximately 25-30% in the cerebral cortex and platelets compared to healthy individuals. Histochemical studies have also revealed abnormally low cytochrome-c oxidase activity in the dentate gyrus, as well as in the CA4, CA3, and CA1 regions of the hippocampus. This decline is linked to a decrease in the expression of messenger RNA (mRNA), particularly in the mid-temporal region of the brains of AD Patients [71].

Mitochondrial impairment in AD can trigger two damaging processes: the overproduction of harmful free radicals and a marked decrease in energy supply. Impairment in key metabolic enzymes, including pyruvate dehydrogenase, oxoglutarate dehydrogenase, and components of the oxidative phosphorylation system, has been well documented. In cultured fibroblasts from AD patients, oxoglutarate dehydrogenase activity has been measured at approximately 50% of normal levels. Furthermore, positron emission tomography (PET) studies have shown reduced regional cerebral glucose metabolism at rest throughout the neocortex, with this decline closely correlating with dementia severity [72].

VII. CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ALZHEIMER DISEASE

Alzheimer's disease is marked by memory impairment, often referred to as mild cognitive impairment (MCI), that is initially subtle but progressively worsens and eventually becomes severely disabling. Its clinical symptoms often resemble normal age-related changes and overlap with other types of dementia, making diagnosis challenging. Limited awareness among caregivers sometimes leads to the belief that nothing can be done to alleviate symptoms. Enhancing knowledge about AD can support better management, improve patient outcomes and reduce care costs. Common clinical symptoms include confusion, impaired judgement, language difficulties, visual disturbances, agitation, social withdrawal and hallucinations. In some cases, patients may also experience seizures, Parkinsonian signs, increased muscle tone, myoclonus, incontinence and mutism. The disease typically lasts 8-10 years, though duration may range from 1 to 25 years. According to the literature (Tanzi and Bertram, 2005), AD is a progressive chronic neurodegenerative condition characterised by global cognitive decline affecting memory, orientation, judgment and reasoning [73].

VIII. DIAGNOSIS

Detecting AD is difficult because clear symptoms often do not appear until several years after the onset of the disease. The diagnostic process can be expensive and time-consuming, requiring evaluation by a skilled clinician. In recent years, research has indicated that language impairment is among the earliest signs of cognitive

decline, suggesting that speech and language features may serve as biomarkers in early dementia detection. A definitive diagnosis of AD can only be confirmed by brain autopsy, which typically reveals a high density of neurotic plaques, neurofibrillary tangles and vascular amyloid - hallmark neuropathological markers of the disease. Evidence also points to cerebrovascular abnormalities - such as structural alterations, atherosclerotic lesions, and impaired blood flow regulation as early indicators of AD. Reduced cerebral blood flow is considered one of the most consistent pathological deficits associated with the condition.

Word retrieval is often assigned using a picture description task. In addition to word retrieval processes, these tasks allow assessing lexical and syntactic complexity, the decline of which has also been reported in dementia.

Memory deficit also contributes to the tendency to repeat words and concepts, which can result in communication errors, lower coherence, and lower information density. Repetition can manifest in spontaneous speech or a fluency test. Typical fluency tests are:

- Semantic verbal fluency (SVF) tasks and
- Phonemic verbal fluency (PVF) tasks

In the semantic verbal fluency test, participants are asked to name as many words in one minute as they can form the same semantic category or begin with the same letter in the case of PVF[74].

IX. TREATMENT

Since a deficiency of acetylcholine (ACh) plays a major role in Alzheimer's disease (AD), increasing ACh levels is a key therapeutic goal. Several strategies have been explored to achieve this, including the use of acetylcholine (ACh) precursors, muscarinic and nicotinic receptor agonists, ACh releasers, and AChE inhibitors. The first AChE inhibitors approved specifically for AD treatment, 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-9-aminoacridine (Tacrine), were introduced in 1993. Currently, additional AChE inhibitors, such as Donepezil, galantamine, and Rivastigmine, are available for patients with mild to moderate stages of the disease.

While AChE inhibitors remain among the most commonly prescribed medications for AD, their use is sometimes limited due to their adverse effects. Some reported side effects include anorexia, diarrhoea, nausea, fatigue, muscle cramps, gastrointestinal, cardiorespiratory, genitourinary and sleep disorders. These challenges have prompted researchers to seek new therapeutic agents that can manage AD effectively while minimising or eliminating such side effects.

9.1 Hormone Replacement Therapy -

Animal studies have demonstrated that administering estrogen to estrogen-deficient laboratory animals can restore the number of neuronal synapses and increase the solubility of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) deposits. Estrogen treatment has also been shown to enhance the activity of choline-acetyl transferase, an enzyme essential for acetylcholine synthesis.

9.2 Exercise to prevent AD -

Physical exercise is considered a potential approach to prevent or delay cognitive decline in the ageing brain. Research suggests that exercise may positively influence three key aspects relevant to Alzheimer's disease (AD): vascular physiology, hippocampal volumes and neurogenesis. Regular physical activity may contribute to reducing the incidence of AD, with epidemiological studies and large prospective trials providing promising support for this hypothesis.

Advancing age is often accompanied by reduced cerebral blood flow, which is closely linked to cognitive performance. Moderate-intensity exercise has been shown to acutely increase blood flow to the brain. In a randomised 12-week exercise intervention, participants demonstrated significantly higher cerebral blood flow in the anterior cingulate complex compared to non-exercising controls. Furthermore, engaging in mild to moderate physical activity over the course of years appears to help preserve hippocampal volume (a brain region critical for memory and learning).

9.3 Alliance with Caregivers -

The Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale-Cognitive Subscale (ADAS-Cog) is widely used to measure cognitive function and evaluate treatment efficacy. Additionally, the clinical interview-based Impression of Change Scale with caregiver input (CIBIC-Plus) serves as a global assessment tool frequently used in clinical trials. Research studies have reported changes on the ADAS-Cog of approximately 2.5 to 3.5 points (on a 0 to 70 scale, where a higher score indicates greater cognitive decline) and differences on the CIBIC-plus of 0.3 to 0.5 points (on a 1 to 7 scale, where 1 reflects substantial improvement and 7 indicates marked deterioration).

A range of non-pharmacological interventions has been explored, particularly in nursing homes and long-term care settings, to address behavioral symptoms in AD. These include the use of music therapy, videotaped messages from family members and audio recordings of caregivers' voices, all of which aim to provide comfort, reduce agitation and strengthen emotional connections.

X. NUTRITION AND ALZHEIMER DISEASE

While small doses of free radical scavengers have shown potential benefits as a preventive measure, their effectiveness in individuals with Alzheimer's disease remains unconfirmed. Regular consumption of certain fruits and vegetables with high antioxidant properties has been found to protect against the harmful effects of oxidative stress on signal transduction and nerve growth factors in rats. Additionally, a lower intake of vitamin C has been linked to an increased risk of cognitive decline [75].

XI. ROLE OF MEDICINAL PLANT TO TREAT ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

For centuries, herbal therapy has been widely used in the healthcare system worldwide; however, its potential therapeutic benefits have yet to be fully explored. A significant number of literatures suggest that this traditional approach has the potential to improve human health, which has led to an increase in the use of herbal medicines by the people. This is because the different parts of the plant contain different concentrations of many active substances. Most of them are present in all parts of the plant, like flowers, seeds, leaves, stem, bark and roots. The extracts of various herbal plants have been evaluated for treating neurodegenerative diseases over the years, and researchers have obtained various outcomes. Some plants that are used to treat symptoms of cognitive disorders are discussed below.

i. *Centella asiatica*

Centella asiatica, a member of the Chibelliferae family, is widely recognised for its medicinal properties. Its leaves are traditionally used as a potent herb to support nervous system function and enhance memory. In Ayurveda, a formulation containing four herbs, including *C. asiatica*, is prescribed to slow the ageing process and prevent dementia. Combining the herb with milk is believed to further enhance memory. The essential oil extracted from its leaves contains monoterpenes such as bornyl acetate, α -pinene, β -pinene and γ -terpinene, which also inhibit AChE. Experimental studies in mice have shown that *C. asiatica* leaf extract exhibits sedative, antidepressant and cholinomimetic activities, effects that were blocked by atropine. These findings suggest that the herb may be beneficial in managing symptoms of depression and anxiety in AD while also enhancing cholinergic activity and cognitive performance. Additionally, the aqueous extract of *C. asiatica* leaves has been found to improve learning and memory in rats, as well as regulate the dopamine, serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine), and noradrenaline systems in the brain. This suggests that the polar compound present in *C. asiatica* leaves may play a crucial role in enhancing cognitive function by modulating the neurotransmitter system in the CNS.

ii. *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha)

Withania somnifera, a woody shrub belonging to the Solanaceae family, has demonstrated notable neuroprotective properties. The methanolic extract of its root has been shown to promote dendrite growth in human neuroblastoma cells in an *in vitro* study, in a dose-dependent manner. Further root preparation of this plant significantly reduces neuronal degeneration in the hippocampal region of the stressed rats, suggesting its potential as a neuroprotective agent in neurodegenerative diseases. Furthermore, glycowithanolides present in *W. somnifera* have exhibited anxiolytic and antidepressant effects in animal models, indicating their potential therapeutic application in managing symptoms of Alzheimer's disease (AD) [76].

iii. *Ginkgo Biloba*

Ginkgo biloba, a member of the Ginkgoaceae family, has long been traditionally used in Iran to alleviate memory impairment associated with poor blood circulation and abnormalities. The plant has been extensively studied for its potential role in managing cognitive disorders. EGb761 from *G. biloba* extract has shown favourable effects on cerebral circulation and neuronal cell metabolism, particularly on the muscarinic cholinergic system, and exhibits antioxidant activity. EGb761 was also neuroprotective against β -amyloid and NO-induced toxicity *in vitro* and could reduce apoptosis in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* settings. *G. biloba* extracts have also been evaluated for their effect on cognitive function. Treatment with *G. biloba* extracts reduces scopolamine-induced amnesia in rats and increases

memory retention in both young and old rats. In mice, it also improves short-term memory. The activity is perhaps due to vasodilatory flavonoids. But the compound responsible for the observation may require further investigation.

iv. *Melissa Officinalis*

Melissa officinalis (Lamiaceae) leaves have been used as a medicinal plant for more than 7,000 years. In European medicine, *M. officinalis* was used as a calming and strengthening remedy to treat migraines, melancholia, neuroses, and hysteria. The plant has been praised for promoting longevity and enhancing memory. In 1951, John Hill stated that *M. officinalis* was good for CNS disorders. *M. officinalis* has been the subject of research regarding its potential as a sedative and anxiolytic activity that may be appropriate to provide symptomatic relief for behavioral problems like agitation in AD. *M. officinalis* leaf was reported to ease mild anxiety and nervousness in a double-blind study. Other activities of *M. officinalis* leaf extract that may be useful for AD therapy include its antioxidant effects and binding to muscarinic and nicotinic receptors *in vitro*, which suggest that its favorable effects on cholinergic function in AD patients may occur [77].

v. *Albizia adianthifolia*

Acanthifolia extracts were tested for anti-AChE activity in different fractions. Fractions from methanolic ethyl acetate, chloroform and n-hexane extract showed strong IC-50 values 11.80±0.88, 10.04±1.67, 17.44±1.74 and 128.38±1.51 (µg/ml), respectively.

vi. *Huperzia species*

Belonging to the family Lycopodiaceae, it has been utilized in China for over 1,000 years to treat a variety of neurological and cognitive disorders. There are eight *Huperzia* species reported. *H. serrata*, *H. epinosana*, *H. weberbaueri*, *H. squarrosa*, *H. brevifolia*, *H. compacta*, *H. crassa*, and *H. tetragona*. Out of which five species show anti-cholinesterase activity. The alkaloid-enriched fraction of the aerial parts of *H. serrata*, whose major constituent was Huperzine A (approximately 0.5%), presented an IC50 of 5.96 µg/ml. Further alkaloid extracts from *H. quadrifariata* and *H. reflexa* reveal *in vitro* acetylcholinesterase activity and also appear to have very effective *in vivo* effects, implying that the *Huperzia* species could still be a promising source of compounds with pharmaceutical interest for AD [78].

Huperzine A, derived from *Huperzia serrata*, is used in Traditional Chinese Medicine as an anti-inflammatory, analgesic, to alleviate memory loss, and for promoting circulation. It is prescribed by name QianCeng Ta. Huperzine A is isolated from the moss *Huperzia serrata*, a lycopodium alkaloid related to the quinolizidine alkaloids, and it inhibits AChE in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. In cognitively impaired aged rats, Huperzine A improved the memory retention process. Additionally, in a multicenter, double-blind trial, Huperzine A significantly improved memory and behaviour in AD patients and was reported to be more selective for AChE than BuChE. It was also found to be less toxic than synthetic AChE inhibitors like Donepezil and Tacrine. Huperzine A is also reported to decrease neuronal cell death induced by glutamate toxicity; it may favorably affect other neurotransmitter systems to improve memory and protect cortical neurons against β-amyloid-induced apoptosis *in vitro*. Huperzine A may also have potential in alleviating memory deficits and neuronal damage, making it potentially beneficial in the treatment of dementia⁷⁹.

vii. *Hemidesmus indicus*

H. indicus belongs to the family Apocynaceae and has been used for the treatment of AD. The hydroalcoholic extract of *H. indicus* has significant AChE inhibitory activity (IC-50= 28.40±0.92µg/ml). *In vitro* AChE inhibitory activities of the root extract of *H. indicus* were also reported.

viii. *Curcuma longa* (turmeric)

Turmeric is a rhizomatous herbaceous perennial plant of the family Zingiberaceae. It is used as a spice, colouring agent, and in traditional medicine throughout the Asian region. The active constituents are mainly curcuminoids and turmeric oils. Curcumin is the principal curcuminoid that imparts the yellow colour. Turmeric, due to its antiseptic, anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial properties, has long been used in the Indian system of medicine to treat a variety of conditions. This versatile spice helps detoxify the liver, balance cholesterol levels, stimulate digestion, fight allergies and boost immunity. A study shows that in Southeast Asian countries, where turmeric is commonly used as a spice, it can lower the incidence of AD. Other studies suggest that the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory properties of turmeric are associated with a reduced risk of AD. Again, when fed to aged mice with advanced plaque deposits similar to those of AD, curcumin reduced the amount of plaque deposition. It reduced oxidative damage and reversed the amyloid pathology in an AD transgenic mouse. Direct injection of curcumin into the brains of mice with AD not only hampered further development of plaque but also reduced the plaque levels. AD symptoms

characterised by inflammation and oxidation were also cured by curcumin's powerful antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.

Additionally, a low dose of turmeric (160 ppm) reduced proinflammatory cytokine levels associated with the neuroinflammatory cascade involved in neuritic plaque pathogenesis. Based on the promising findings in animal models, clinical trials of oral curcumin supplementation in patients with early AD are already underway. According to a clinical trial study on curcumin in 27 AD patients, oral supplements containing up to 4g/day of curcumin were found to be safe.

ix. Shankhpuspi

Shankhpuspi is a widely used medicinal plant in India. Several species, including *Convolvulus pluricaulis*, *Clitoriaternatea*, *Convolvulus microphyllus*, and *Evolvulusalsinoides*, represent it. Traditionally, the whole plant has been incorporated into various formulations as a nervine tonic to enhance memory and cognitive function. Phytochemical studies of this plant have identified a diverse range of secondary metabolites, including triterpenoids, flavanols, glycosides, anthocyanins, and steroids, that are believed to contribute to its nootropic, memory-enhancing, and other pharmacological activities. The plant is thought to exert calming effects on the nervous system by regulating stress hormones, including adrenaline and cortisol, which are commonly recommended for managing stress, anxiety, mental fatigue and insomnia-like conditions. Experimental studies support its cognitive benefits. The ethanolic, ethyl acetate, and aqueous extract of CP have demonstrated significant improv

ement in learning and memory in an animal model, with the ethanolic extract also showing notable *in vitro* antioxidant activity. A dose-dependent enhancement of memory was observed in mice that were administered extracts of CP. Similarly, 7 days of administration of CP extracts enhanced memory in aged mice. Hippocampal regions associated with learning and memory function showed a dose-dependent increase in acetyl cholinesterase activity with CP treatment. More specifically, the administration of aqueous root extract of CT to neonatal rats resulted in improved retention and spatial learning performance, indicating the memory-enhancing properties of CT. In addition, a significant increase in acetylcholine content was observed in the hippocampi of CT-treated rats in comparison with age-matched controls. An increase in acetylcholine content in the hippocampus may be the neurochemical basis for their improved learning and memory. Young rats incubated with aqueous root extract of CT showed a significant increase in passive avoidance learning and retention.

x. Jatamansi (*Nardostachys jatamansi*)

The rhizomes and roots of the plant have medicinal value. They contain a variety of sesquiterpenes and coumarins. The sedative sesquiterpene valeranone is a major component of the essential oil extracted from the roots. Other terpenoids include spirojatamol, nardostachysin, jatamols A and B and calarenol. Jatamansi is the predominant coumarin. Studies on its role in the CNS revealed that the extracts of *Nardostachys jatamansi* alleviated all the symptoms of chronic fatigue syndrome (CFS) in rats. An alcoholic extract of this plant administered to both young and aged mice significantly improved learning and memory and also reversed the amnesia induced by diazepam and scopolamine. Furthermore, it is reverse ageing-induced amnesia due to the natural ageing of mice, suggesting that the compound in this extract may be beneficial in restoring memory in patients with dementia.

xi. Guggulu

Guggulu is an oleogum resin found in several plant species, including *Commiphora mukul*, *C. molmol*, *C. abyssinica*, *C. burseraceae*, and *C. wightii*. The resin exudes from the cracks and fissures in the bark and from incisions in it. The oleogum resin of guggulu is a mixture of 30 % to 60% water-soluble gum, 20%-40% alcohol soluble resin and about 8% volatile oils. Guggulu contains ferulic acids, phenols and other non-phenolic aromatic acids that are potent scavengers of superoxide radicals and could be beneficial in the treatment of AD and other oxidative stress-related diseases. The resin has been used in the treatment of arthritis, inflammation, obesity and lipid metabolism. A recent study reveals that guggulipid has a remarkable beneficial effect against the streptozotocin-induced memory deficit model of dementia. The effect may be due to its cholesterol-lowering, antioxidant, and anti-acetylcholinesterase activity. These observations suggest guggulipid as a potential anti-dementia agent.

xii. *Bacopa monniera*

The plant belongs to the family Plantaginaceae and is an annual plant found in wet, marshy, and damp areas of the Indian subcontinental regions. The plant is used in Ayurvedic medicine to improve memory and intellect. Ethanol extract of the rhizome and aerial part of the plant possesses nootropic activity. This may be due to the bacosides, which can induce membrane dephosphorylation, leading to a concomitant increase in protein and RNA synthesis in a specific brain area. According to another finding, enhancement

of protein kinase activity in the hippocampus and cognitive enhancement are due to its modulatory effect on the cholinergic system. In another study, it was found that a standardised baccoside-rich extract from the leaf and stem of the plant reversed cognitive deficits induced by colchicine and ibotenic acid. Additionally, the extract reversed the depletion of ACh, ChAT activity, and decreased muscarinic receptor binding in the frontal cortex and hippocampus. A similar extract of the *B. monniera* plant demonstrated antioxidant activity in the rat frontal cortex, striatum, and hippocampus [79].

xiii. *Panax ginseng*

P. ginseng, belonging to the Araliaceae family, is a well-known traditional Chinese herb that has been used for centuries across East Asian countries, including China, Japan and Korea. Over time, extensive scientific studies have demonstrated its potential as a neuroprotective agent. These protective effects on the nervous system make it valuable in both the prevention and treatment of various neurological conditions, such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease, and strokes. The herb's primary active compound, ginsenoside, has been found to exhibit both neuroprotective and anti-amyloidogenic properties [80].

xiv. *Clitoria ternatea*.

C. ternatea, commonly known as a parasite butterfly, is a herbaceous plant with vibrant blue, purple and white flowers. It is widely used in Ayurvedic medicine for various purposes and is also grown as an ornamental plant. The rhizome of the plant has been used in Ayurvedic medicine as a brain tonic and is reputed to promote memory and intellect. An *in vivo* study of the ethanol extract from the rhizome and aerial parts of the plant reveals a memory-enhancing effect, which is also associated with increased levels of ChAT and Ach. In another study, an aqueous rhizome extract increased the level of Ach in the rat hippocampus, which may be due to an increase in ChAT. An ethanol extract from various aerial parts of the plant exhibited a sedative effect in mice [81].

xv. *Polygala tenuifolia* Wild

Polygala tenuifolia, a member of the Polygalaceae family, has been used for a long time in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM). The root of *P. tenuifolia* is valued for its cerebrotonic and cardiogenic properties. It has traditionally been prescribed as a sedative and tranquillizer for conditions such as amnesia, forgetfulness, neuritis, nightmares, and insomnia. According to the "Chinese material and medica", the root of the plant is believed to enhance willpower, strengthen memory, improve comprehension and increase physical vitality. Several herbal formulations containing *P. tenuifolia* root have been evaluated for their effects on neurodegenerative diseases. One such preparation, DX-9386, is composed of four herbs, including *P. tenuifolia* root extract. Experimental studies in animal models of Alzheimer's disease (AD) have demonstrated that DX-9386 enhances motor activity, reduces lipid peroxidation, alleviates memory impairment, prolongs the lifespan of senescence-accelerated mice, and mitigates ethanol- and scopolamine-induced memory deficits in mice. Similarly, "Kami-Utan-To" (KUT), a Japanese Traditional Medicine containing 13 herbs including *P. tenuifolia* root, has demonstrated neuroprotective effects. KUT was found to dose-dependently enhance choline acetyltransferase (ChAT) activity and increase Nerve Growth Factor (NGF) secretion *in vitro*, and to improve passive avoidance behaviour in animal studies, suggesting its therapeutic potential in neurological disorders [82].

XII. Conclusion

In the present study, we emphasized Alzheimer's disease (AD) as a major health threat among the elderly population. This review discusses the underlying causes, clinical manifestations, diagnostic methods and currently available treatment. While also addressing the role of medicinal plants in disease management and highlighting existing research gaps to encourage further scientific investigation. The integration of traditional plant-based remedies with modern pharmacotherapeutic targets in AD, and assessing the potential of traditional medicinal plants in its treatment.

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